

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MONTAGNON****FIRST NAME: SOPHIE****PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. KABIRU GULMA**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 7%

The author used the following software: (Microsoft 365 Apps for enterprise, Windows 10 Enterprise)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. The imperative of consistency (EUCLID 2024, 41)
2. Style supports clarity (EUCLID 2024, 52)
3. Style supports meaning (EUCLID 2024, 26)
4. Plagiarism avoidance (EUCLID 2024, 34)
5. Style and professionalism (EUCLID 2024, 4)

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDITORIAL STYLE COMPLIANCE

1) INTRODUCTION

I recently had a pretty unpleasant experience at work. I prepared a nice slideshow for a remote presentation using my working entity's proper graphic chart and template. I sent it to my supervisor for her kind review, thinking it would mostly be a content approval question. Surprisingly, all her comments were on the format. She had checked every slide and noticed the font and some layouts were incorrect. I did not detect a content transfer issue from another slideshow because the font was similar. I must admit that I thought: is it that important? It was a technical presentation with a regular audience; no stakes, I would say. A few weeks later, when I started attending the ACA-401D Course, I thought again about this experience because the main question is the same, even in a very different context: why is compliance with a designated editorial style so important?

My response is that it is critical. Hence, the instrumental help provided by manuals, guides, and other guidance documents and the criticality of Cleenewerck and Gulma's ACA-401D Coursepack (EUCLID 2024) for a doctorate student like me, overwhelmed by the excitement of this new learning journey. This document offers a comprehensive gathering of key rules for writing academic papers.

This response paper will highlight a few key points supporting my statement. After the first part on the imperative of consistency, I will elaborate further on how it supports clarity and meaning. The next point will be on the importance of respecting intellectual property. Finally, I will explore the link between styles and professionalism.

2) THE IMPERATIVE OF CONSISTENCY

Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines consistency as an “agreement or harmony of parts or features to one another or a whole” or a “harmony of conduct or practice with profession” (Merriam-Webster, Inc. 2024). As a sign of its importance, the word consistency appears ten times in the Coursepack document, especially three times on one page (EUCLID 2024, 41).

Reading academic papers is not easy, and consistency in style offers the reader some comfort. The variability would be distracting and give room for interpretation or doubts about the meaning of these changes, if any. Hence, **the imperative of consistency**.

Consistency, though, is a laborious exercise. It needs rigor and tireless editing efforts, a quality that florid and creative minds may sometimes lack. Additionally, while the necessity of style guides is debatable for native speakers, for non-native speakers, especially those, like me, not very talented in language proficiency, they are invaluablely helpful.

3) STYLE SUPPORTS CLARITY

Clarity is always required in academic writing (EUCLID 2024, 52).

E.B. White, in the introduction of the 1979 edition of *The Elements of Style* by William Strunk Jr., with Revisions, an Introduction and a Chapter on Writing by E.B. White (Strunk and White 2023, 10), could not have told it better:

All through *The Elements of Style* one finds evidences of the author's deep sympathy for the reader. Will felt that the reader was in serious trouble most of the time, floundering in a swamp, and that it was the duty of anyone attempting to write English to drain this swamp quickly and get the reader up on dry ground, or at least to throw a rope.

For example, an editorial **style supports clarity** by guiding the writers to use punctuation. Semi-colons help when listing many items, especially with commas (EUCLID 2024, 18).

It helps to write words correctly. The wise use of hyphens clarifies words with potentially misleading prefixes (EUCLID 2024, 46).

A final example is that it helps write technical, complex content. Writing about numbers is challenging, and the guidance provided by editorial styles is instrumental (EUCLID 2024, 48).

With guidance on format, fonts, layout, headings, sentence length, and so on, editorial styles provide clarity to a document (EUCLID 2024, 41).

4) **STYLE SUPPORTS MEANING**

The fact that style supports meaning is probably the most counter-intuitive one. I tend to intuitively think that the meaning is in the words themselves, in what I write, no matter how I write it. I realized I was wrong during this first step of this new learning journey.

Foremost, an editorial **style supports meaning**. Meaning is in the correct orthography of a word (EUCLID 2024, 26) and the wise use of contractions, abbreviations, and expressions (EUCLID 2024, 59). It is not by chance that Strunk's first line of his book is about possessives (Strunk and White, 2023, 11).

5) **PLAGIARISM AVOIDANCE**

Respect for intellectual property is a critical value in academic research. When it comes to writing, this value takes the form of **plagiarism avoidance**. Beyond copy-pasting sentences or paragraphs, plagiarism occurs any time a source is used in a document without properly mentioning its origin (EUCLID 2024, 34).

Editorial guides give many details about ensuring the source is given legitimate credit. From my point of view, it is a very challenging exercise in academic writing because it involves extreme attention to details, information usually seen as secondary (like the editor or a date of consultation), different features of format like font, size, bold or italics, margins, indentations and so on. It is also difficult to review since there is no other way than carefully checking all the details.

6) **STYLE AND PROFESSIONALISM**

Checking all the details to ensure compliance with a style is professionalism (EUCLID 2024, 3).

Sir David Clementi, Chairman of the BBC Board, in the foreword of BBC's Editorial Standards, expresses clearly the strong link between **style and professionalism**:

The public and BBC audiences rightly demand the highest editorial standards from the BBC and it is the job of the BBC Board to ensure that our content – across all services and genres – meets those.

7) CONCLUSION

These two weeks have been a fabulous step into the world of academic writing. I found enlightenment in reading editorial manuals, which I could not have anticipated (even if reading my organization's was an experience I loved in the past and that I frequently repeat every time I need to verify something). Writing is not only about having thoughts to share. The thoughts, the ideas, are only the beginning. Talent in writing includes talent in editing. Editing requires time, energy, and tirelessness. However, it is an invaluable gift given to an audience and the most resounding proof of respect and humility.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Merriam-Webster Dictionary. 2024. "Consistency." Accessed August 11, 2024. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/consistency>.

William Strunk Jr., E.B. White. 2023. *The Elements of Style: Fourth Edition*. Independent Publisher.

BCC. 2024. "The BBC's Editorial Standards." Accessed August 12, 2024. <https://downloads.bbc.co.uk/guidelines/editorialguidelines/pdfs/bbc-editorial-guidelines-whole-document.pdf>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.